

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-1-21-IC-2% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	20230310
Vial:	4	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 1 21
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	290.0nm
Run Time:	25.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 290.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/10/2023 11:22:05 CST		
Date Processed:	3/10/2023 14:47:22 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.320	270451	19.90	16031
2	11.518	412588	30.36	19759
3	13.073	399032	29.36	17778
4	20.444	277019	20.38	8045

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-177-1-IC-2% asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0
Vial:	94	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 2 177
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	290.0nm
Run Time:	24.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 290.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	6/27/2022 17:48:17 CST		
Date Processed:	3/10/2023 14:46:08 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.245	159877	1.52	11537
2	11.180	10045792	95.56	579016
3	12.706	30626	0.29	1720
4	19.623	275938	2.62	9074